

Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics, Consumer Decision-Making Process, and Sales Performance of Herbal Distributors

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15501775

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the extent of influence of radio advertising on the characteristics and consumer decision-making process and the sales performance of herbal distributors in Negros Occidental for the current year, 2025. A descriptive correlational research design was used in this study. The data were gathered using a researcher-made questionnaire. The respondents of this study were the 274 herbal distributors and 384 loyal customers of the company having heard of the radio advertisement aired about their product offerings within Negros Occidental. Purposive and convenient sampling were used in selecting the participants whose characteristics or status suited to the criteria and interest in the attainment of objectives of this study. The statistical tools utilized were Mean, Standard Deviation, Mann Whitney, Kruskal Wallis, and Spearman's Rho. The results showed that great extent of influence of radio advertisement both on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process. While the Level of sales performance determined by sales volume and net profit on herbal products by herbal distributors. Moreover, the analysis revealed that there is a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics when grouped according to sex, age and monthly income. The study also highlighted the significant positive correlation between the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process. In terms of the level of sales performance, the study concluded that there is a significant difference in the level of sales performance according to their profile variables. The distributors operating for over 10 years significantly differed from those with 3 to 6 years, indicating higher sales performance with increased experience.

Keywords: radio advertisement, consumer characteristics, consumer decision-making process, sales performance, Negros Occidental

Introduction

Background of the Study

Radio is an effective medium for creating awareness about herbal products. The repetitive nature of radio ads helps in reinforcing brand messages, which is crucial for products in niche markets like herbal remedies (Paul et al., 2017). A study found that repeated exposure to radio advertisements helps in creating brand recognition and familiarity, which increases the likelihood of purchase (Silayo & Mtallo, 2024; Musa & Ismail, 2013). Additionally, a study found that radio ads, when aired consistently, contribute to increased brand recognition (Caldwell and McIntyre, 2018).

Radio remains one of the most accessible forms of media in the Philippines, especially in rural and remote areas. According to a study by the Philippine Statistics Authority (PSA), radio penetration is widespread in the country, with millions of Filipinos tuning in regularly. This widespread access allows companies to promote herbal products to a large, diverse audience. For example, radio stations often have specific programs targeted at health-conscious consumers, creating an opportunity for herbal product brands to advertise (2022). Radio continues to be a significant source of information for Filipinos, as it reaches even the 'remotest' areas. Because the radio is described as the most 'pervasive' medium (Media Ownership Monitor [MoM], 2017), it is not surprising that hundreds of regional and community radio stations operate in the country.

Statement of the Problem

The study determined the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process and the sales performance of herbal distributors in Negros Occidental for the current year, 2025.

1. What is the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics in terms of: beliefs/ attitudes, values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, lifestyle
2. when they are taken as a whole and when they are grouped according to age, sex, and gross monthly income?
3. What is the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process in terms of: problem solving, information search, purchase, post purchase, evaluation
4. when they are taken as a whole and when they are grouped according to age, sex, and gross monthly income?

5. 3. What is the level of sales performance in terms of: Sales volume, Net profit rate
6. when taken as a whole and when grouped according to length of business operation, location, and capitalization?
7. 4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics when grouped according to their profile variables?
8. 5. Is there a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process when grouped according to their profile variables?
9. 6. Is there a significant relationship between extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process?
10. 7. Is there a significant difference in the level of sales performance when grouped according to business profile variables?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics when grouped according to their profile variables.
2. There is no significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process when grouped according to their profile variables.
3. There is no significant relationship between extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process.
4. There is no significant difference in the level of sales performance when grouped according to business profile variables.

Theoretical Framework

The consumer behavior process is a complex journey influenced by various factors. The relationship between consumer characteristics, decision-making, and radio advertisements can be understood through well-established models of consumer behavior. These models highlight how consumers respond to marketing stimuli and the impact of media channels, including radio advertisements, on their purchasing decisions. This study gleaned on the Black Box Model (1969) as it pertains to incorporating recent research on consumer behavior from 2020 and beyond.

The Black Box Model focuses on understanding the internal processes that lead to a consumer's response to marketing stimuli, which includes advertising. From research of Kumar and Singh (2021) found that consumer decision-making based on radio ads often depends on these personal and psychological characteristics. Ads tailored to these factors are more likely to trigger positive responses and influence buying behavior. This study measures the influence of radio advertisements to Consumer Characteristics' psychological factors such as perception, motivation, and attitudes. A consumer's response to a radio ad depends on how they interpret the message and whether it resonates with their emotional or rational needs. In terms of decision-making process, consumer receptiveness to radio ads act as a stimulus that triggers responses at various stages of the decision-making process, such as need recognition, information search, and purchase intention. Rajagopal, and Raman, (2022) highlight that radio ads effectively influence consumers at the "need recognition" stage, especially when they target specific motivations such as scarcity or exclusivity.

Conceptual Framework

This study evolved within the concepts on the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process and sales performance of selected herbal distributors around Negros Occidental. The researcher brought into detail the consumer characteristics such as beliefs, attitude, motive, knowledge, values, perceptions and lifestyles. Moreover, the concepts about consumer decision making process involved problem solving, information search, purchase, post purchase, and evaluation. The study determined the significant relationship between extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process. On the other hand, the herbal distributors' sales volume and net profit rate determined with the consideration of business length of operation, location and capitalization. And therefore, business considerations on radio advertisements would not solely depend on the frequency of their air time ads but rather on the improvement of their advertising content and quality in totality as the consumer will be more inclined in looking into the worth of the product advertised on radio as it is in reality.

Scope and Limitation

The scope of the study focused on gathering data about the extent of influence of radio advertisement on customer characteristics and consumer decision-making process among 384 consumers in Negros Occidental who have been listening to radio advertisements on herbal products. The level of sales performance was assessed by 274 herbal distributors whose products are radio advertised within Negros Occidental. This research determined the extent of radio advertisement influence to the consumer characteristics in terms of their beliefs/attitudes, values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, and lifestyle. While the consumer decision-making process involved the following factors:

problem solving, information search, purchase, post purchase and evaluation. Moreover, the level of sales performance was determined by sales volume and net profit rate of herbal products advertised by herbal distributors. This study conducted the data gathering from February 2025 to March 2025. The customers of herbal distributors who are not engaged in radio advertisement are not qualified to become respondents. The gathering of data was through Online forms and face-to-face process.

Significance of the Study

This study will be significant to the following groups:

Herbal Distributors. As business owners, they will benefit from this study, as it could help them to decide whether to continue or conduct a marketing strategy which involves radio advertising that may promote herbal products and will result to higher sales and profitability.

Radio Station Managers in Negros Occidental. This study is going to be beneficial to radio stations because this study opens opportunities to every business owner to bring their products into advertisement. The more radio advertising clients the company will have, the higher the sales radio stations can have.

Marketers or Marketing Personnel. By knowing the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process, the marketers or marketing personnel will have the confidence and sufficient knowledge on how to reach consumers and meet their needs and the same time, considering their company's interest.

Literature Review

Relevant studies and literature are presented in this chapter to refer to influence of radio advertisements to consumer characteristic in term of their beliefs or attitudes values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, lifestyle. Studies on influence of radio advertisements to consumer decision making in terms of problem solving, information search, post purchase, and evaluation. More reading has been added regarding sales volume and net profit rate of the business.

Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics

Traditional advertising used radio in advertising as it is perceived as the cheaper and faster way of introducing products to the customers aside from print advertising. Though other companies believe that advertising in radio is quite slow in product launching or market introduction, such outlook really differs from agency to agency.

Radio Advertisement on Consumer Beliefs/Attitudes

It is a consideration for a company to check the beliefs or attitudes uphold in a certain community or place where they put up their business since the people's way of thinking and culture effect on how they behave on buying something or products endorsed through radio advertising. A study by Sama (2019), indicated that marketers invest in various media platforms to influence consumer behavior. Advertisement on every media platform has a different composition that engages the consumers in a distinct way. Digitalization has led to changes in consumers' media habits. Hence, a deeper understanding of advertisements on different media platforms and its implications on consumer behavior need to be established.

Radio Advertisement on Consumer Values

A study by Butt, et al. (2022), indicated that consumer buying behavior was an important aspect in every marketing strategy to produce maximum output from the market. Their study determined how advertisement affects consumer buying behavior and brand loyalty by considering a mediator between brand awareness and the moderating role of perceived quality. According to Tanuwijaya and Gunawan (2021), advertising value was considered to be an important factor to determine the consumers' willingness to purchase advertised products or services. Their study assessed that entertainment and informativeness were found to have significant influences towards the purchase intention. However, irritation was found to not have a significant influence towards the purchase intention. The data analysis also showed that entertainment, informativeness, and irritation were found to have a positive correlation with the purchase intention.

Radio Advertisement on Consumer knowledge

Consumer's characteristics often depends on what they know about the product being advertised on the radio. García-Nieto et al. (2021) in their book entitled "Social Responsibility and Misleading Advertising of Health Products on the Radio. The Opinion of the Professionals. International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health" "Misleading advertising is a serious detriment to consumers and, therefore, to one of the groups of interest of the

advertising agencies and the advertiser with whom it is related. In the case of advertising for health products, where audiences are more vulnerable, this fact is more reprehensible. Advertisers are aware that today brands, and therefore companies, must combine their sales objectives with a strategic vision of the organization based on ethics, transparency and CSR. Nowadays, advertising has a twofold function: its role as a commercial activity and, on the other hand, it has a social dimension by directly influencing contemporary ways of life. Advertising represents one of the most regulated activities in Spain, but from a social point of view its management is more complicated and the consumer is not always protected."

Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process

Radio Advertisement on Problem-Solving

The best way to influence customers' purchasing decisions is to rate the radio is the most convenient and economical medium for influencing consumers' intentions to make a purchase. This indicates that there is fierce competition among the advertising channels. Academic research should be conducted on how radio advertising affects customers' inclinations to buy in this technologically advanced society. Until radio stations started to portray slow revolutions between 1912 and 1920, radio was considered a mainstay of family pleasure. Station owners began obtaining licenses while also looking for ways to make the platform self-sufficient. Radio advertising began at this time, as seen by Dennis's first internationally recognizable radio ad in 1922. Radio has always been a progressively popular advertising medium influencing consumers into purchasing.

Radio Advertisement on Post Purchase

To affect consumer decision-making process, marketers spend money on a range of media outlets. All media platform's advertisements have a unique composition that attracts viewers in a unique way. A study by Tsai (2020), explored the resonance of advertising benefits of storytelling in marketing from the perspective of consumers' purchase intention.

Methodology

Research Design

This study used a descriptive correlational research design. Descriptive research is a research method describing the characteristics of the population or phenomenon studied. This descriptive methodology focuses more on the what of the research subject than the why of the research subject. The descriptive research method primarily focuses on describing the nature of a demographic segment without focusing on why a particular phenomenon occurs. In other words, it describes the subject of the research without covering why it happens. In this study the researchers will determine the extent of influence of the radio advertisement on the consumer buying behavior and sales performance. Consumer characteristics has several considerable factors such as belief, motives, values, knowledge, perceptions and lifestyles. Moreover, factors on consumer decision-making process include problem solving, information search, purchase, post purchase and evaluation while sales performance have sales volume and net profit rate used to come results for sales performance.

Participants of the Study

The participants of this study were the 274 herbal distributors and 384 loyal customers of the company having heard of the radio advertisement aired about their product offerings for the year 2024-2025. The participants were believed to be patronizing Clinica De Alternativo Medicina and Wellness Center, Inc. company's product after hearing the radio advertisement. Herbal distributors should have a physical store and selling herbal products.

Purposive and convenient sampling was used in selecting the participants whose characteristics or status suited to the criteria and interest in the attainment of objectives of this study. The researcher chose the consumer participants aged between 18 years old to 59 years old, and they have heard the radio advertisement about herbal products aired for the favor of the distributor chosen by the researcher and have been available to answer the survey.

Research Instrument

The researcher-made instrument is composed of two sets. One set of questionnaires was to measure the extent of influence of radio advertisement to consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process, with 22 survey item questions for consumer characteristics; and 20 for consumer decision making process.

The data gathering instrument validated using the Lawshe CVR criteria where each of the 10 panel of experts will give their rating to each item of the survey instrument (Ramzan Sama, 2019). Out of 23 items for consumer characteristics questionnaire, 22 items included and 1 item excluded. Out of 20 items for consumer decision-making process questionnaire, all are included and nothing was excluded. Same with the items for herbal distributors, 10

items were included in the questionnaire. The conduct of validity test among panel of experts resulted 0.96 Content Validity Index, that makes the researcher-made instrument valid.

The data taken from the pilot testing will be used for the reliability test. The reliability test will be done using Cronbach's Alpha. The acceptable value for the Cronbach's Alpha must be .70 and above to pass the reliability test. The researcher conducted a face-to-face mode of communication to the 30 radio solid listeners and 30 distributors of herbal medicines. The reliability test resulted 0.96 in the 30 consumer responses, and 0.91 in the 30 distributor responses.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher sent a letter to the company's manager requesting permission to conduct the study within his/her premises. The researcher administered the questionnaires both in person or face-to-face mode and online form to customers after asking for their consent as well. For the online distribution of questionnaires to the consumers, the researcher gave a letter with a QR code of the link for the google form to the staff to be answered by every customer who visited the herbal store by using their mobile phones.

For the distribution of the questionnaires for the distributors, the link for the google form was provided to the distributors of herbal products of Clinica De Alternativo Medicina and Wellness Center.

Upon retrieval of data, the survey instrument and responded online forms were properly filed, correctly encoded for data processing, and stored properly for future verification.

Data Analysis

After the data collection activity, the data will be encoded and examined using statistical tools. Objective 1 which measured the extent of influence of radio advertisement on the consumer characteristics in terms of beliefs/ attitudes, values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, lifestyle as a whole and when grouped according to age, sex, and gross monthly income, was answered using mean, and standard deviation.

Statement of problem 2, which measured the extent of influence of radio advertisement on the consumer decision-making process in terms of problem solving, information search, purchase, post purchase, evaluation as a whole and when grouped according to age, sex, and gross monthly income, was answered using mean, and standard deviation. Statement of problem 3, which is the determination of the level of sales performance using sales volume and net profit rate was answered using mean and standard deviation. While inferential questions 4, 5, and 6 determine the significant difference between the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process when group according to their profile variables and the level of sales performance when group according to business profile variables was answered using Mann Whitney and Kruskal Wallis. Inferential question 7 on the determination of the significance relationship of the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process, Spearman's Rho was used. Finally, thematic analysis was used to answer objective 8 which will discover IEC materials that can be proposed at the bottom of the study.

Ethical Consideration

Research principles was given full attention by the researchers. Authorization from the Clinica De Alternativo Medicina and Wellness Center, Inc. was properly secured. Informed consent forms were signed by the participants. Participants' personalities and responses was dealt with utmost confidentiality. Principles of secrecy, honesty, objectivity, intellectual property rights, legalities, and many other ethical issues will also be taken into full consideration.

In addition, the researchers observed to the best of their knowledge and abilities the right to patent, and citation of relevant information quoted in this scholarly undertaking to give credits to the original researcher/s and/or author/s.

Results

Influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics

Table 1 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of beliefs and attitudes. The statement "*I give due attention to the advertisements before I buy the products*" (M=4.30, SD=0.71) received the highest rating, followed by the statement "*Through advertisements, I feel assured that the products I bought are effective*" (M=4.300, SD=0.66). The findings showed that consumers are highly mindful of advertisements prior to making purchases. Additionally, the findings indicated that consumers have an assurance that the products they consume, are effective, through advertisements. A study by Gupta & Chopra (2020) showed

that social media usage influences consumer satisfaction in the stages of information search and alternative evaluation, with satisfaction getting amplified as the consumer moves along the process towards the final purchase decision and post-purchase evaluation.

Table 1

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Belief/Attitude

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.30	Very Great Effect	0.57
1. I give due attention to the advertisements before I buy the products.	4.30	Very Great Effect	0.71
2. I easily draw my attention to the brand being advertised.	4.29	Very Great Effect	0.63
3. Through advertisements, I feel assured that the products I bought are effective.	4.30	Very Great Effect	0.66

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 2 presented the extent of influence in terms of values. The belief that "Advertisements are reliable (functional value)" (M=4.21, SD=0.65) emerged as the top response, followed by the statement "I assume that advertisements are guaranteed by regulating agencies i.e., BFAD, etc. (conditional value)" (M=4.16, SD=0.66), and "I appreciate the advertisements emphasize the different product variants, for example, in terms of sizes, and varying scents/flavors. (Epistemic value)" (M=4.12, SD=0.65). The findings showed that consumers have a strong trust in the practicality and dependability of advertised products, and give value on the legality of the advertisements' claims. Additionally, the findings showed that consumers give appreciation on the advertisements with the needed details about the product being advertised. A study by Karmoto (2024) found that consumer reviews on social media significantly influence purchasing decisions, especially those reviews that include visuals and testimonials from other users. Additionally, brand transparency and responsiveness to consumer feedback highlight the importance of openness in fostering trust.

Table 2

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Values

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.15	Great Effect	0.52
1. I assume that advertisements are reliable (functional value).	4.21	Great Effect	0.65
2. I assume that advertisements are guaranteed by regulating agencies i.e., BFAD, etc. (conditional value).	4.16	Great Effect	0.66
3. I value each information about the products I bought through advertisements (personal value).	4.12	Great Effect	0.64
4. I regard the product endorsers in the advertisements who authentically experienced the products' claims. (Social value)	4.12	Great Effect	0.65
5. I appreciate the advertisements emphasize the different product variants, for example, in terms of sizes, and varying scents/flavors. (epistemic value)	4.13	Great Effect	0.63

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 3 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of knowledge. The statement "I educate myself about the existence of the products I bought through advertisements" was most prominent (M=4.49, SD=0.63), followed by the statement "Advertisements allow me to easily find the products I need" (M=4.46, SD=0.67) and lastly the statement "Advertisements help me to know about new products" (M=4.41, SD=0.67). The findings emphasized the role of advertisements in enhancing product awareness and the accessibility of the product in terms of details and information need by the consumers. A study by Farooq and Maqbool (2024) explored how advertising interacts with customers and influences both internal and external organizational processes and activities. Additionally, the study sought to address misconceptions surrounding advertising's purpose and societal impact, particularly regarding its perceived manipulation of consumers for monetary gain.

Table 3

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Knowledge

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.45	Very Great Effect	0.55
1. Advertisements help me to know about new products.	4.41	Very Great Effect	0.67
2. I educate myself about the existence of the products I bought through advertisements.	4.49	Very Great Effect	0.63

3. Advertisements allow me to easily find the products I need. 4.46 Very Great Effect 0.67
 Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 4 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of motives, the highest-rated statement was "It gives me more interest when my favorite celebrity promotes the product I bought" (M=4.39, SD=0.59). The findings highlighted the persuasive power of celebrity endorsements in influencing consumer interest. In the study of Elliott et al. (2019), radio advertisements that include expert testimonials or celebrity endorsements have a significant effect on consumer perceptions, especially for health-related products. Moreover, Johnston and Davis (2017) found that radio ads that feature health professionals or recognized experts tend to improve consumer trust in the advertised product.

Table 4
 Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Motives

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.49
1. I look for the advertisement before I buy the products.	4.38	Very Great Effect	0.63
2. I easily remember the products I patronize through advertisements.	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.63
3. It gives me more interest when my favorite celebrity promotes the product I bought.	4.39	Very Great Effect	0.59
4. Advertisements give me courage to maintain the product I buy.	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.64

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 5 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of perception, "Most of the advertisements create interest to buy the products" was rated the highest (M=4.34, SD=0.64). The findings indicated that advertisements effectively stimulate consumers' buying interest. A study by Selvi et al., (2023) indicated that effective advertising has a significant impact on consumer buying behavior. A well-designed advertisement can generate interest, create awareness, and positively influence consumer attitudes towards a brand, ultimately leading to increased sales.

Table 5
 Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Perceptions

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.50
1. Advertisements shape my perception about the products.	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.62
2. Most of the advertisements are necessary to watch, read and/or listen for the customer before purchase.	4.31	Very Great Effect	0.65
3. Most of the advertisements create interest to buy the products	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.64
4. Promotion through advertisement brings amusement to consumers	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.64

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 6 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of lifestyle, respondents agreed most with the statement "Advertisements enhance the quality of my loyalty to the brand I am consumer of" (M=4.38, SD=0.61). The findings showed that consistent advertising reinforces brand loyalty. The study of Zulfikar (2023) described effective marketing strategies to build strong brands and increase brand awareness and consumer loyalty.

Table 6
 Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics in terms of Lifestyle

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.51
1. I regularly watch, read or/and listen to the advertisement to make myself updated about the products/brands	4.29	Very Great Effect	0.63
2. I enjoy listening, reading, and watching advertisements.	4.32	Very Great Effect	0.63
3. Advertisements enhances the quality of my loyalty to the brand I am consumer of lifestyle.	4.38	Very Great Effect	0.61

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 7 presented the summary of extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics. Overall, the computed mean score for *consumer characteristics* was also very great (M=4.31, SD=0.43). The finding suggested that the general influence of advertisements on consumer behavior is notably strong across all categories assessed. A study by Abideen & Saleen (2011) demonstrated an overall normal association between the variables but in-depth analysis found that emotional response of consumer purchase behavior is the variable that results into strong association with the consumer buying behavior. It is true that people purchase those brands with which they are emotionally attached.

Table 7

Summary of Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics

Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.31	Very Great Effect	0.43
1. Beliefs/Attitudes	4.30	Very Great Effect	0.57
2. Values	4.15	Very Great Effect	0.52
3. Knowledge	4.45	Very Great Effect	0.55
4. Motives	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.49
5. Perceptions	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.50
6. Lifestyle	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.51

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process

Table 8 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of problem-solving. The statement "I often get convinced about the claims made by the companies in the advertisements" received the highest mean (M=4.38, SD=0.60) while the statement "Advertisements can change my perception regarding the products or brands" (M=4.26, SD=0.59) received the lowest mean. The findings indicated that advertisements strongly influence consumer beliefs about product claims. A study by Iduwo (2023) showed the analysis of how advertisements affect consumers' purchasing decisions is an essential component of the study on marketing. The primary cause is the fact that advertising significantly affects how consumers perceive items, which in turn affects how they behave while making purchases.

Table 8

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process in terms of Problem solving

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.48
1. Advertisements can change my perception regarding the products or brands	4.26	Very Great Effect	0.59
2. I often get convinced about the claims made by the companies in the advertisements	4.38	Very Great Effect	0.60
3. Advertisement helps me to recognize the real over the fake products	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.62
4. Advertisement assists me to find the product that I needed for some time.	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.64

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 9 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of *information search*, the highest-rated item was "The advertisements are easy to understand" (M=4.38, SD=0.60), while the lowest-rated was "Advertisements are informative and provides detailed description about products". The findings suggested that clarity and simplicity in advertisement messaging are vital in facilitating informed choices. A study by Light and Fernbach (2024) suggested that consumers' simplicity/complexity perceptions reflect the dimensionality of their mental representations of brands, and the relationship between simplicity and lower risk is attenuated when additional brand dimensionality is framed in terms of redundancy. The findings cast doubt on the degree to which evoking simplicity is a uniformly positive marketing strategy and encourage practitioners to more thoughtfully consider simplicity's implications for consumer and firm welfare.

Table 9

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process in terms of Information Search

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.35	Very Great Effect	0.46

1. Advertisements are informative and provides detailed description about products	4.31	Very Great Effect	0.62
2. Advertisements demonstrate the way of usage of the brand or product	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.61
3. Advertisements allow me to discover new features of the products I bought	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.61
4. The advertisements are easy to understand.	4.38	Very Great Effect	0.60

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 10 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of purchase behavior. The item "Through advertisement, I am informed of discounts that get me excited every purchase" garnered the highest rating (M=4.37, SD=0.61), while the item "Most of the time, advertisements prompt me to buy the products" (M=4.29, SD=0.59) garnered the lowest rating. The findings reflected how promotional content stimulates buying activity. The more exciting promos being advertised, the more consumers get excited for their purchase. One of the items of marketing mix is price. Consumers are convinced to purchase for every discount promoted. The study by Dawood & Shamout (2016) determined the impact of the most used tools of sales promotion in retail sector such as: coupons, sample, price discount and buy one get one free on consumer buying behavior from two aspects; brand switching and customer loyalty.

Table 10

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process in terms of Purchase

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.45
1. Most of the time, advertisements prompt me to buy the products	4.29	Very Great Effect	0.59
2. The advertisements of promotional schemes generally compel me for a purchase	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.60
3. Advertisements influence the frequency of my purchase	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.61
4. Through advertisement, I am informed of discounts that get me excited every purchase	4.37	Very Great Effect	0.61

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 11 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of post-purchase behavior. The responses indicated that consumers are most impacted by "Advertisements lead me to make a repeat purchase of the same brand" and "Advertisement spending is somewhat successful in persuading people to make a repurchase" (both M=4.36, SD=0.63). The finding showed that effective ads foster brand loyalty and continued patronage. Additionally, the findings indicated that consumers who are being amused by the advertisements, are persuaded for repeat purchase of the product they consume. A study by Rane et al., (2023) explored effective strategies for improving customer loyalty through quality service. One of the key drivers of customer loyalty is customer satisfaction, which can be influenced by service and product quality, brand loyalty, and company reputation. Measuring and understanding customer satisfaction is vital for improving customer loyalty.

Table 11

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process in terms of Post Purchase

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.47
1. I feel satisfied when I get exposed to the advertisement of the brand, I am a consumer of	4.31	Very Great Effect	0.60
2. Advertisements lead me to make a repeat purchase of the same brand	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.61
3. I recommend to other people the products I buy through advertisement	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.63
4. Advertisement spending is somewhat successful in persuading people to make a repurchase.	4.36	Very Great Effect	0.63

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 12 presented the top-rated indicators consistently reflected a very great extent of influence in terms of evaluation category, the top-rated item was "Effective advertisements have the power to arouse feelings and strengthening the bond between me, as consumer and the brand" (M=4.37, SD=0.60), while the lowest-rated was "I am confident that the products I bought helped confirm the information from advertisements" (M=4.24, SD=0.60). The findings indicated underscoring the emotional connection formed through well-crafted advertisements. A study

by Vrtana & Krizanova (2023) showed that advertising with emotional appeal has different effects on consumers' purchasing behavior depending on their age, advertising with emotional appeal affects consumers more negatively than positively, and the use of emotional appeal in the advertising space creates an emotional connection with the brand.

Table 12

Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process in terms of Evaluation

Items	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.32	Very Great Effect	0.47
1. I am confident that the products I bought helped confirm the information from advertisements.	4.24	Very Great Effect	0.60
2. Effective advertisements have the power to arouse feelings and strengthening the bond between me, as consumer and the brand.	4.37	Very Great Effect	0.60
3. The advertisement is truly updated in providing information that made by purchase experience validated.	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.60
4. The frequency of advertisements allows me to understand the necessity to purchase the product.	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.64

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 13 presented the summary of extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process. Overall mean score for *decision-making* was also very high (M=4.34, SD=0.40), further emphasizing the powerful role that advertisements play in influencing consumer judgments across all stages of the buying process. A study by Soti (2022) revealed a positive correlation between advertising exposure, consumer attitudes, and purchase intentions, emphasizing the persuasive power of advertising in shaping consumer perceptions and influencing their decision-making process.

Table 13

Summary of Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process

Indicators	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.40
1. Problem Solving	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.48
2. Information Search	4.35	Very Great Effect	0.46
3. Purchase	4.33	Very Great Effect	0.45
4. Post Purchase	4.34	Very Great Effect	0.47
5. Evaluation	4.32	Very Great Effect	0.47

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Level of sales performance

Table 14 presented the top-rated herbal product categories based on distributors' assessments. For sales volume, the highest-rated product was "*Vitamins*" (M=4.83, SD=0.38), closely followed by "*Food Supplements*" (M=4.78, SD=0.41), indicating that these items dominate in terms of quantity sold. These results suggested strong consumer demand and consistent purchasing behavior for these health-related products. A study by Suhartini (2024) indicated that consumer perceptions of health products are significantly influenced by personal experiences and information obtained from social environments and media. Trust in the brand and the transparency of manufacturers in providing information also play an important role in shaping consumer decisions.

Table 14

Level of Sales Performance in terms of Sales Volume

Types of products	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.59	Very High	0.37
1. Food Supplements	4.78	Very High	0.41
2. Liniment Oil	4.32	Very High	0.54
3. Herbal Soap	4.43	Very High	0.62
4. Herbal Coffee	4.59	Very High	0.55
5. Vitamins	4.83	Very High	0.38

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 15 presented the top-rated herbal product categories based on distributors' assessments. In terms of net profit, the same top-performing categories were identified, with "*Vitamins*" again receiving the highest mean score (M=4.85,

SD=0.37), followed by "Food Supplements" (M=4.79, SD=0.41). These findings highlight the profitability of these two products, suggesting not only high sales but also favorable margins. A study by Rajendran & Kamarulzaman (2023) highlighted herbal-based product issues, major safety concerns associated with consuming herbal products, and significant challenges associated with effective safety and quality monitoring.

Table 15
Level of Sales Performance in terms of Net Profit rate

Types of products	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.59	Very High	0.37
1. Food Supplements	4.79	Very High	0.41
2. Liniment Oil	4.29	Very High	0.55
3. Herbal Soap	4.42	Very High	0.63
4. Herbal Coffee	4.63	Very High	0.53
5. Vitamins	4.85	Very High	0.37

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Table 16 presented the summary of level of sales performance. Across all products, the total mean for both volume and net profit was rated *very high* (M=4.59, SD=0.37), underscoring the strong overall performance of the herbal product line. This suggests a robust and sustainable market, particularly for products positioned as health-enhancing and preventive solutions. A review by Dr. Sam (2019) concludes that the use of herbal medicines and initiatives to develop it will enable the developing countries to look inward rather than continuing to rely on expensive, imported medicines having side effects.

Table 16
Summary of Level of Sales Performance

Types of products	M	Interpretation	SD
Overall	4.59	Very High	0.37
1. Sales Volume	4.59	Very High	0.37
2. Net Profit Rate	4.59	Very High	0.37

Note: Extent of Influence, 5- Very Great extent, 4- Great extent, 3- Moderate extent, 2- Low extent, 1 -Very Low extent

Significant Differences in the extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics and Consumer Decision-Making Process

Tables 17 showed that Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine the significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics, with results showing a significant difference for age [U=13954.000, p=0.000]. The older group reported a significantly higher extent of influence. There was a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics in terms of sex [U=15692.000, p=0.031], with the male group reporting a significantly higher extent of influence. Regarding gross monthly income, a significant difference was found [$\chi^2(3)=28.028$, p=0.000]. Post hoc analysis for gross monthly income revealed that consumers earning Php 5,000 and below reported a significantly lower influence compared to those earning over Php 20,000. However, no significant differences were found between other income groups. The influence of radio advertisements on consumer characteristics is further supported by the findings of Ahakwa et al. (2021), who explored the effectiveness of various advertising media, including television, radio, newspaper, and outdoor advertisements. Their study, conducted among university students in Ghana, revealed that while television advertisements had the greatest impact on purchase decisions, radio advertisements also had a significant and positive influence. The study employed Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) to analyze consumer responses, reinforcing the idea that different demographic groups respond differently to advertisement channels.

Table 17
Difference in the Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics

Variable	U	z	p
Age	13954.000*	-4.005	0.000
Sex	15692.000*	-2.160	0.031
Gross Monthly Income	χ^2 28.028*	df 3	p 0.000

Note: *the difference in the means is significant when $p \leq 0.05$

Post Hoc Test for Gross Monthly Income

Gross Monthly Income	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
Php 5,000 and below - Php 5,001 to Php 10,000	-17.781	35.413	-0.502	0.616

Php 5,000 and below - Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	-43.053	32.375	-1.330	0.184
Php 5,000 and below - Over Php 20,000	-91.086	31.702*	-2.873	0.004
Php 5,001 to Php 10,000 - Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	-25.272	20.231	-1.249	0.212
Php 5,001 to Php 10,000 - Over Php 20,000	-73.305	19.136*	-3.831	0.000
Php 10,001 to Php 20,000 - Over Php 20,000	-48.032	12.660*	-3.794	0.000

Table 18 showed that Mann-Whitney U test was used to determine the significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on decision-making. The results showed a significant difference in the extent of influence based on age [U=14596.500, p=0.001], with the older group reporting a significantly higher level of influence. In terms of sex [U=14957.000, p=0.004], male consumers reported a significantly higher extent of influence. Regarding gross monthly income [$\chi^2(3)=25.028$, p=0.000], post hoc analysis revealed that consumers earning Php 5,000 and below reported a significantly lower influence compared to those earning Php 10,001 to Php 20,000, those earning over Php 20,000, and those earning Php 5,001 to Php 10,000. Additionally, significant differences were found between consumers earning Php 10,001 to Php 20,000 and those earning over Php 20,000. No significant differences were found between other income groups. This finding aligns with the study conducted by Pelegrin et al. (2022), which investigated the role of entrepreneurial orientation in micro-businesses and its impact on sales growth performance. Using statistical approaches such as multiple regression and analysis of variance, the study confirmed that entrepreneurial-oriented traits significantly contribute to business success, reinforcing the idea that specific business profile characteristics influence financial performance. Applying the Resource-Based View (RBV), the study classified entrepreneurial orientation as a crucial resource in achieving competitive advantage, further supporting the notion that internal business attributes play a key role in shaping sales performance. This parallel between the current study's results and existing literature emphasizes the importance of business characteristics in determining financial success.

Table 18

Difference in the Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Decision-Making

Variable	U	z	p
Age	14596.500*	-3.412	0.001
Sex	14957.000*	-2.845	0.004
Gross Monthly Income	χ^2 25.028*	df 3	p 0.000

Note: *the difference in the means is significant when $p \leq 0.05$

Post Hoc Test for Gross Monthly Income

Gross Monthly Income	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
Php 5,000 and below - Php 5,001 to Php 10,000	-49.892	35.413	-1.409	0.159
Php 5,000 and below - Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	-66.973	32.375*	-2.069	0.039
Php 5,000 and below - Over Php 20,000	-109.516	31.702*	-3.455	0.001
Php 5,001 to Php 10,000 - Php 10,001 to Php 20,000	-17.081	20.231	-0.844	0.398
Php 5,001 to Php 10,000 - Over Php 20,000	-59.624	19.136*	-3.116	0.002
Php 10,001 to Php 20,000 - Over Php 20,000	-42.543	12.660*	-3.360	0.001

Relationship between extent of influence of Radio advertisement on Consumer characteristics and extent of influence of Radio advertisement on Consumer Decision-Making Process

Table 19 showed that the Spearman's rank correlation was used to assess the relationship between the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and decision-making. The results showed a strong, significant positive correlation between these two variables [$r_s(382)=0.743$, p=0.000], indicating that as the extent of influence of radio advertisements on consumer characteristics increases, so does its influence on decision-making. These findings mean that there is similarity between consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process. Almost the same behavior portrayed by the consumers when they are classified according to their beliefs, motives, knowledge, lifestyle, decision-making processes like purchase, information search and so on. A study conducted by Haider et al., (2017), states that consumers are more motivated to buy a product when they see an advertisement of it somewhere; they also feel safe to buy a product that they have seen advertisement of. Consumer develops a level of trustworthiness for a brand they have seen advertisement of. They were even noted to collect information of products from advertisement, get to know about the usage and benefits of product and then make a purchase decision based on that

Table 19

Relationship between Extent of Influence of Radio Advertisement on Consumer Characteristics and Decision-Making

Variable	r_s	df	p
Consumer Characteristics x Decision-Making	0.743*	382	0.000

Note: *correlation is significant when $p \leq 0.05$

Differences in the Level of Sales Performance

Table 20 presented the Kruskal-Wallis H test results on the differences in the level of sales performance among distributors based on their length of business, location, and capitalization. The analysis revealed significant differences in sales performance when grouped according to length of business [$\chi^2(2)=14.797$, $p=0.001$], location [$\chi^2(2)=10.185$, $p=0.006$], and capitalization [$\chi^2(3)=71.531$, $p=0.000$]. Post hoc analysis showed that distributors operating for over 10 years significantly differed from those with 3 to 6 years ($p=0.000$) and 7 to 10 years ($p=0.008$) of business, indicating higher sales performance with increased experience. In terms of location, distributors from Bacolod City had significantly higher sales performance compared to those from Northern Negros ($p=0.008$) and Southern Negros ($p=0.006$), while no significant difference was observed between Northern and Southern Negros ($p=0.926$). Regarding capitalization, significant differences were found across almost all groups. Distributors with higher capitalization (Php 40,001 and above) consistently outperformed those with lower capitalization, particularly those with Php 20,001 to Php 40,000 and Php 20,000 and below (all $p < 0.05$), suggesting a strong association between greater capital and better sales performance. The finding is supported by the study of Spotts et al., (2022) states that while studies of advertising efficiency pave the way for investigations that incorporate a broader set of marcom activities to understand efficient resource allocation across the marketing mix, to date there has not been such a study. The present research analyzes marketing communication's influence on firm sales performance in a media context that includes traditional paid advertising, digital advertising, sales promotions, traditional publicity, and social media.

Table 20

Difference in the Level of Sales Performance among Distributors

Variable	χ^2	df	p
Length of Business	14.797*	2	0.001
Location	10.185*	2	0.006
Capitalization	71.531*	3	0.000

Note: *the difference in the means is significant when $p \leq 0.05$

Post hoc test for Length of Business

Length of Business	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
3 to 6 years - 7 to 10 years	-19.830	10.571	-1.876	0.061
3 to 6 years - Over 10 years	-83.063	23.068*	-3.601	0.000
7 to 10 years - Over 10 years	-63.233	23.921*	-2.643	0.008

Post hoc test for Location

Location	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
Bacolod City - Northern Negros	30.777	11.634*	2.646	0.008
Bacolod City - Southern Negros	31.934	11.634*	2.745	0.006
Northern Negros - Southern Negros	1.157	12.469	0.093	0.926

Post hoc test for Capitalization

Capitalization	Test Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Test Statistic	Sig.
Php 20,000 and below - Php 20,001 to Php 40,000	13.260	34.667	0.382	0.702
Php 20,000 and below - Php 40,001 to Php 60,000	-68.457	33.352*	-2.053	0.040

Php 20,000 and below - Over Php 60,000	-117.324	34.822*	-3.369	0.001
Php 20,001 to Php 40,000 - Php 40,001 to Php 60,000	-81.717	12.790*	-6.389	0.000
Php 20,001 to Php 40,000 - Over Php 60,000	-130.584	16.241*	-8.040	0.000
Php 40,001 to Php 60,000 - Over Php 60,000	-48.868	13.204*	-3.701	0.000

Discussion

The results indicated that the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics in terms of beliefs/ attitudes, values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, and lifestyle, as a whole, had a very great influence on their characteristics. Moreover, the result indicated that the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process in terms of problem solving, information search, purchase, post-purchase, and evaluation had a very great level of influence. The result indicated the level of sales performance in terms of sales volume and net profit rate, as a whole, had very high level of sales performance. Furthermore, the finding showed a strong, significant positive correlation between the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process. Moreover, the findings revealed significant differences in sales performance when grouped according to length of business, location, and capitalization. Post hoc analysis showed that distributors operating for over 10 years significantly differed from those with 3 to 6 years and 7 to 10 years of business, indicating higher sales performance with increased experience. Lastly, in terms of location, distributors from Bacolod City had significantly higher sales performance compared to those from Northern Negros and Southern Negros, while no significant difference was observed between Northern and Southern Negros.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions have been drawn:

The consumer characteristics in terms of beliefs/ attitudes, values, knowledge, motives, perceptions, and lifestyle, were influenced very greatly by radio advertisements. Moreover, the consumer decision-making process in terms of problem solving, information search, purchase, post-purchase, and evaluation were also influenced very greatly by radio advertisements. There is a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics, the same with the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process, there is a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement. The study also highlighted the significant positive correlation between the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer decision-making process. In terms of the level of sales performance, the study concluded that there is a significant difference in the level of sales performance according to their profile variables. The distributors operating for over 10 years significantly differed from those with 3 to 6 years, indicating higher sales performance with increased experience.

Recommendations

In view of the findings of this study, the following recommendations have been made:

From the findings and conclusion of the study that there is a significant difference in the extent of influence of radio advertisement on consumer characteristics and consumer decision-making process when group according to sex, age and monthly income, the following are recommended: first, to future researchers who would like to take up the same subject of study to increase the respondents to a significant number. Second, include other variables not used in the study. And lastly, conduct a study regarding the effectiveness of the different strategies on consumer buying behavior.

From the findings and conclusion of the study that there is a significant difference in the level of sales performance when group according to sex, age and monthly income, the following are recommended: first, to future researchers who would like to take up the same subject of study to increase the respondents to a significant number. Second, include net profit rate to add substance to the study. And lastly, conduct a study regarding the effectiveness of the different strategies on consumer buying behavior in relation to level of sales performance and net profit rate.

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